

Compounding Natural Fibers with High Process Temperature-Thermoplastics with Solid-State Shear Pulverization (SSSP) : Flax / PA6

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NATURAL FIBER USE FOR BIOCOMPOSITES

specific mechanical
property enhancement

acoustic and vibration
damping

non-abrasive,
process-friendly

sustainable and
CO₂ neutral

chemical resistance

natural image

REALISTIC APPLICATIONS

automotive

alternative mobility

sports equipment

architecture

packaging

household

NATURAL FIBERS AND GLASS

Property	E- GLASS	FLAX	HEMP	BAMBOO	JUTE	RAME	SISAL	COTTON
Density [g/cm ³]	2.55	1.45	1.48	1.4	1.46	1.5	1.33	1.51
Tensile Strength [MPa]	2000-2400	800-1500	550-900	750-950	400-800	500	600-700	400
Stiffness [GPa]	70-74	55-75	40-65	30-50	10-30	45-65	12-38	8-12
Specific Stiffness [G Pa *cm ³ /g]	27-29	38-52	27-44	21-36	7-21	30-43	9-29	5-8
ε [%]	3	1,5 - 2	1.6	1.9	1.8	2	2-3	3-10

Source: « Flax & Hemp fibres, a natural solution for the composite industry » Publication

SPECIFIC FOCUS: SHORT DISCONTINUOUS FIBERS

Short
flax fibers

(quasi)-
random orientation

Thermoplastic
matrix

Mass Fabrication of Commercial, Industrial Products

mechanical property enhancement

cost reduction

weight reduction

environmental footprint reduction

MELT COMPOUNDING: A COMMERCIAL PROCESS

Twin Screw Extrusion (TSE)

- ▣ Suitable for mass fabrication
 - Automated and continuous
 - Commercial scale-up
 - Low cost
 - Well-established
- ▣ Limitations
 - Thermoplastics
 - Only short fibers can be fed
 - Heat degradation
 - May require additional tactics/tricks

CHALLENGE 1: HEAT

Thermogravimetry: typical flax fiber (dried), 10°C/min ramp

- Flax thermally degrades 180 – 200 °C
- Also depends on exposure time (compound + molding)
- Melt compounding limits the matrix options to commodity plastics

CHALLENGE 2: FIBER LENGTH / ASPECT RATIO

- Elementary fibers are only adhering together with pectin
- $L_c = (\sigma_f d) / (2 t)$ (need high AR for effective load transfer)
- Advantageous elementary fiber properties and size

Typical length of an elementary fiber = ~ 2cm

	technical	elementary
Modulus	30 – 70 GPa	39 – 79 GPa
Strength	~ 800 MPa	~ 1500 MPa

PROPOSITION: CHILLED COMPOUNDING

Solid-State Shear Pulverization (SSSP) = modified TSE
(Berstorff ZE-25UTX, D=25mm, L/D = 36)

- Vision for mass fabrication
 - Automated and Continuous
 - Commercial scale-up
 - Versatile input
 - Ready for any shape/size
- Some of the TSE challenges are addressed
 - No more heat degradation
 - No tricks or tactics, just simple shear and compression

SSSP TECHNOLOGY

Solid-State Shear Pulverization (SSSP)

□ Unique process technology

- Processing in the solid state
- Avoiding thermal degradation
- Shear and compression dictate changes (not kinetics, transport...)
- No compatibilizers, solvents, aids
- Safe/environment conscious
- Simple and versatile

□ Applicable in composites

- Effective mixing
- Compatibilization
- De-lamination/ de-bundling action proven in nanocomposites

CNT

nano graphite

PROCESSING PARAMETERS

Model Study of high-process temperature thermoplastics/ natural fiber composites

- ❑ Polyamide 6 (Tm ~220 °C) matrix
- ❑ Flax fiber (native from Belgium)
- ❑ SSSP Process Conditions

- ❑ Compare also with hand-mix, and TSE
- ❑ Parameters kept constant: 20 wt% flax loading, drying / molding conditions, 200rpm screw speed

POST-COMPOUNDING

Output

- Flakes/powder (SSSP)
- Pellets (TSE)

Drying

- Before injection-molding
- Before testing

Injection molding

- Benchtop injection molder

Mechanical Testing

- Tensile (ASTM 1708)
- 3-pt bending (ASTM 790)

Structural Characterization

- Optical microscope
- SEM
- μ -CT

RESULTS: SSSP VS. TSE

PA6 / 20 wt% scutched flax comparison

RESULTS: SSSP VS. TSE

PA6 / 20 wt% scutched flax comparison

vs.

vs.

Micro-CT

Flax fibers are "reduced" in different ways

FLAX FIBERS BEFORE AND AFTER SSSP

As-Received scutched flax
(nominal length~2mm)

SSSP-Processed:
Extracted flax from PA6-flax composite

SSSP debundled flax into
elementary fibers

PROCESS “HARSHNESS”

PA6 / 20 wt% straw flax comparison

Micro-CT

Higher shear → shorter fibers & homogeneous mixing

PROCESS “HARSHNESS”

PA6 / 20 wt% straw flax comparison

HandMix

SSSP (low)

(medium)

(high)

Optical microscopy
(cross-sectional)

Most tech.
fibers

some elem.
fibers

many
elem.
fibers

few elem.
fibers left

Higher shear → debundling into elementary, then destroying

WITH FIBER TYPE

PA6 / 20 wt% flax type comparison, SSSP Low

straw

scutched

flaxtape

Micro-CT

Flax tape starts with >10x length fibers, but ends with similar lengths

WITH FIBER TYPE

PA6 / 20 wt% flax type comparison, SSSP Low

Optical microscopy
(cross-sectional)

Significant debundling into elementary fibers

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

- SSSP has potential for compounding natural fibers with high process-thermoplastics
 - Process optimization with flax type, loading, length, etc.
 - Expand to other natural fibers (hemp, bamboo, coir, etc.)
- Technical → Elementary fiber separation observed
 - Preservation of the aspect ratio is key
- Micromechanical Modelling: $P_c = P_f V_f \mathbf{A} + P_m (1 - V_f)$
 - $\mathbf{A} \sim$ orientation, length, efficiency
- Quantifying compatibility / adhesion

EXTENSION: SSSP-LFT WITH NATURAL FIBERS

Solid-State/ Melt Extrusion (SSME) = combined SSSP and TSE
(Berstorff ZE-25UTX, D=25mm, L/D = 34)

PP / flax LFT

Flax roving
(Safilin, France)

PP
(Total USA)

▣ Continuous extrudate

- Retaining long-fiber lengths
- Debundling to elemental fibers
- Post-processing-ready

▣ Future challenges

- Mechanical reinforcement
- Application to higher-melting plastic matrices (e.g. PA-6)

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